

More than the Sum of its Parts – Specialised Information Services and Text+ as complementary Infrastructures

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NFDI consortia and Specialised Information Services (FID) have a complex relationship. Both address various phases of research processes in their respective scientific fields. However, such similarity in scope does not necessarily imply contention – especially when taking into account the specific approach of the NFDI consortium Text+ which is primarily organised around data domains and thus across scientific fields. Text+ has set itself the goal of preserving language- and text-based research data in the long term, and enabling their broad and diverse use in academia and beyond. Besides more than 30 participating institutions in the consortium, Text+ cooperates with a large number of further academic stakeholders on different levels and in different ways. These collaborations guarantee a close contact with the diverse scientific communities and an understanding of their needs.

The DFG-funded FID programme (DFG 2023) was set up to grant fast and direct access to specialised research literature and information. Based in scientific libraries and driven by their research communities, each FID provides additional services tailored to their specific field. These services are as diverse as the respective disciplines and can range from consulting and research support to digital publication platforms for scientific output. Through this collaborative approach, each FID has strong links within its respective communities. The various FID institutions are united within a general FID framework and work together in various dedicated sub-networks.¹ 12 FID are currently enrolled as partners within Text+.²

FID play an important role as brokers between the Text+ infrastructure and their shared scientific communities, support the consortium with their expertise, and actively influence the consortium's course of actions. Text+ offers a large competence network. Hence, both networks do have the potential to supplement each other on various levels and to create synergies by collaborating. Additionally, they can benefit from engaging in cross marketing activities. Yet, the concrete implementation of this collaboration also poses major challenges for both sides. Among these are:

- Communication: Currently, both networks employ a wide variety of internal communication channels, between the two networks, and beyond. This plentitude is

¹ For further information on the current number and scope of the FID cf. https://wikis.sub.uni-hamburg.de/webis/images/8/8a/Aktionsplan-FID-Netzwerk_2022-2024.pdf.

² Cf. <https://www.text-plus.org/ueber-uns/weitere-partner/>.

a sign of the networks' openness but it also carries the risk of information loss. It is therefore necessary to establish and curate a clear and efficient communication structure that is both stable and agile.

- Consensus on objectives and measures of cooperation: To identify common goals and formulate concrete actions to be undertaken and how to assign these for the benefit of both partners and their communities.
- Expectation and resource management: To identify available resources, expected outcomes on (and inputs from) each side and to state them transparently in order to overcome reservations.
- Sustainability: Both Text+ and FID implement research infrastructures that need to be sustained in the long term.

Concrete measures to tackle these challenges are resolved in two ongoing series of exchange, the “FID Roundtable” organised by the FID Philosophie and the “FID/Text+ Jour Fixe” (Geißler/Schulz 2022) organised by representatives of the Text+ working group “AG FID Koop” (Geißler et al. 2022), which is specifically dedicated towards initialising and supporting the cooperation with FID. Further measures can also be derived from those Text+ user stories (Rißler-Pipka et al. 2021) supplied by FID. To facilitate communication between the FID and Text+, different channels have been implemented, using NFDI-wide established tools (e.g. Rocket.Chat).

Agreeing on common standards is also a topic of high relevance with regard to the implementation of a Text+ registry that will index and interlink resources from the consortium’s data domains (Collections, Lexical Resources and Editions) (see figure). The data model for cataloguing editions (Gradl et al. 2022) has been developed in close collaboration with the FID who also act as (meta)data providers for the registry. In addition, a co-affiliated position has been installed serving as liaison post between FID and the consortium.

Figure 1: Resources and their context in the Text+ Registry

Another current activity concerns surveying services and expertises provided by FID in order to be able to oversee the complex landscape. This charting – which has been conducted among Text+ partner institutions in a survey before – sets the base for defining competencies and responsibilities in order to complement each other in the best possible way and to identify desiderata.

Consulting researchers, project teams, and institutions on research data management (RDM) is another focus of collaboration. Over decades, the FID and their predecessors, the Special Subject Collections, have built strong relationships with their respective research communities. As a result, researchers often view FID as their natural partners in information processing issues. In the humanities in particular, it is likely that researchers will also turn to their respective FID for guidance on RDM.³ Given the diverse portfolio of each FID and the ever-changing challenges for both researchers and FID, there will not be a single agency that can provide all services and answers. The primary role of FID therefore lies in helping researchers navigate between different infrastructures and identifying possible shortcuts to the most appropriate solutions. Similarly, FID inform the NFDI of researchers' needs so that NFDI consortia may take them into account in their work. On the other hand, cross-disciplinary superstructures such as Text+ and other NFDI consortia can provide both concrete solutions and guidance to the FID. This model not only provides the researcher with a single point of contact but also enables the efficient implementation of RDM standards across a wide range of research areas and communities. A recent example of this dual process is the aforementioned collaborative effort to set up an edition registry.

FID network and Text+ both aim to further intensify their collaboration in the future. Our poster will present the current state and areas of collaboration between FID and consortium and focus on upcoming and planned activities. In addition to highlighting challenges and approaches to tackle them, it will be clarified how networks and infrastructures can be connected not only for mutual benefit but – first and foremost – for the benefit of the entire scientific community.

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³ Some FID already offer information on RDM cf. <https://forschungsdaten.info/wissenschaftsbereiche/geisteswissenschaften/projekte-initiativen-und-netzwerke/fachinformationsdienste-fid-mit-fdm-angebot/>.

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